

Multi-layered
Security
Technologies
for hyper-connected
smart cities

D2.6: Integrated Prototype – first release
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Glossary

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application programming interface
APP	Application
D	Deliverable
DUT	Device under test
EU	European Union
ID	Identifier
IoT	Internet of Things
IRL	Integration Readiness Level
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OS	Operating System
P2P	Peer-to-peer
QoL	Quality of Life
SDK	Software Development Kit
SRA	System Readiness Assessment
SRL	System Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
T&R	Trust and Reputation
UC	Use Case
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WP	Work Package
Y	Year

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the document

This deliverable is the outcome of Task 2.3 “Overall Integration”, which focuses on the overall plan to integrate components and modules developed and deployed in WP4. It also generates the integrated system providing the M-Sec functionalities as they have been specified in WP3.

In order to integrate all the components and modules, an integration plan was devised. In the integration plan a methodology together with a series of best practices, work plans and testing schemes were described. This deliverable provides the first iteration for the integrated prototype achieved following the integration plan.

For clarity, and following the approach taken in the integration plan, the integrations between assets are being presented per Use Case (UC), as each one of them has its own interaction with the assets in Section 3. Although a Global overview can be seen in the Section2.

All subsections in Section 3 include:

- A short description of the Use Case.
- An interaction diagram showing the integration points in a functional view.
- An interaction matrix with all the Integration Readiness Level (IRL) between the assets used in the Use Case.
- A Use Case System Readiness Level (SRL)

Finally, in Section 4 the conclusion extracted from all the work done.

1.2 Relationship to other work packages and tasks

Deliverable D2.6 “Integrated Prototype – first release”, uses as input the M-Sec requirements and architecture introduced in deliverable D3.1 “M-Sec requirements” as well as the developments performed in the WP4 and the methodology written in the deliverable D2.5 “Integration Plan”. As a result, the following deliverables are taken into account:

- Deliverable D2.5 about Integration Plan from Task 2.3.
- Deliverable D3.1 about M-Sec requirements from Task 3.1.
- Deliverable D3.3 about M-Sec architecture from Task 3.2.
- Deliverable D4.1 about IoT Security from Task 4.1.
- Deliverable D4.3 about cloud and data level security from Task 4.2.
- Deliverable D4.5 about P2P level security and blockchains from Task 4.3.
- Deliverable D4.7 about application level security from Task 4.4.
- Deliverable D4.9 about end-to-end security from Task 4.5.

The results of this deliverable will be used as input for Task 2.4, which will validate and evaluate the procedures described in this document.

2.2 IRL matrix

In Table 1 the reference table, with value and description, to understand all values on Interface Readiness Level (IRL) matrixes of the document.

Table 1. Interface Readiness Level definitions.

IRL	Definition/Description
9	Integration is Mission Proven through successful mission operations.
8	Actual integration completed and Mission Qualified through test and demonstration in the system environment.
7	The integration of technologies has been verified and validated with sufficient detail to be actionable.
6	The integrating technologies can accept, translate, and structure information for its intended application.
5	There is sufficient control between technologies necessary to establish, manage, and terminate the integration.
4	There is sufficient detail in the quality and assurance of the integration between technologies.
3	There is Compatibility (i.e., common language) between technologies to orderly and efficiently integrate and interact.
2	There is some level of specificity to characterize the interaction (i.e. ability to influence) between technologies through their interface.
1	An interface (i.e. physical connection) between technologies has been identified with sufficient detail to allow characterization of the relationship.

In the Table 2 which details the interaction matrix, we can see the interaction points between all the assets that are expected to take place in M-Sec. The interactions points show the readiness level of integration between the assets.

Table 2. Overall interaction matrix.

M-Sec

	Caburn Home Monitoring Devices	Companion Database	Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	Ganonymizer	Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	Mobile Wallet	Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	Node-RED	Park Guide	Quorum Blockchain framework	Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	Secure SOXFire	Secured components for devices and gateways	Security Management Tool	SmileCityReport (App)	SmileCityReport (Server)	T&R Model engine/tool	Visualization Tool	TST IoT crowd-counting devices	TST IoT environmental devices	UC4.1 APP	Worldline Connected Care Assistance	Honeypot (IoT POT)
Caburn Home Monitoring Devices			5																						
Companion Database								1	5		1	1										1	6		
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)				3								4													
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)									1		6								1	1			5		
Ganonymizer																3									
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)											5							6						7	
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware						5	6	1	6		1	1			2			1	1				5		
Mobile Wallet									6																
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)										2			2												
Node-RED											5	1													
Park Guide																			3	3					
Quorum Blockchain framework												1												1	
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform												6	1	1											
Secure SOXFire														1									6		
Secured components for devices and gateways																				1	1				3
Security Management Tool																		1							
SmileCityReport (App)																		3							
SmileCityReport (Server)																									
T&R Model engine/tool																									
Visualization Tool																									
TST IoT crowd-counting devices																									
TST IoT environmental devices																									
UC4.1 APP																									
Worldline Connected Care Assistance																									
Honeypot (IoT POT)																									

2.3 Integration descriptions and details

This section describes a list of integration points. Each integration point has a short explanation with relevant information about their status.

Companion Database – Quorum Blockchain framework/Blockchain middleware

The integration between the Companion Database and the Quorum Blockchain framework / Blockchain middleware relies on the need to authorize a person or entity to read the data owned by a third party.

In order to manage this authorisation, a Smart Contract has been developed in order to save the authorised people/entities.

The Smart Contracts gives the possibility to give authorisation, revoke authorisation, check authorisation as a basic set of functionalities.

Worldline Connected Care Assistance – Companion Database

The integration between these two assets has been performed adding a module in the Worldline Connected Care Assistance asset in order to have the usual connection to the database of the application and a new connection that will provide extra security and encryption for the sensitive data.

Worldline Connected Care Assistance – Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)

This integration has the need to sign an NDA in order to keep the confidentiality between developments. At the moment an analysis is conducted in order to see the matching points and to device the implementations needed.

The integrations to the Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio) need a custom development called “bridge” to standardize the data to its ecosystem.

Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio) – Caburn Home Monitoring Devices

This integration has the need to sign an NDA in order to keep the confidentiality between developments. At the moment an analysis is conducted in order to see the matching points and to device the implementations needed.

The integrations to the Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio) need a custom development called “bridge” to standardize the data to its ecosystem.

Companion Database – Security Management Tool

This integration is currently under analysis. The Security Management Tool requires from a server side installation, and some requirements have to be met.

Worldline Connected Care Assistance – IoT Marketplace

This integration is currently under analysis in order to find the best way to feed the IoT Marketplace with the data generated by the application.

Secure SOXFire - Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)

The integration has been totally done. Sensor data sent to Secure SOXFire can be forwarded to the Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio) through the integration.

Secure SOXFire - Secure Mobile Sensing Platform

The integration has been totally done. The IoT devices included in the Secure Mobile Sensing Platform transmit all the sensor data through Secure SOXFire.

Secure SOXFire – SmileCityReport (App & Server)

The integration has been totally done. SmileCityReport (Server) is built atop Secure SOXFire. Pictures taken by SmileCityReport (App) software on a smart phone are transmitted to subscribers through Secure SOXFire.

Secure SOXFire - Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)

The integration has been totally done. Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI) data are transmitted to Secure SOXFire through the Secure Mobile Sensing Platform, then can be forwarded to other platforms including Node-RED and Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio).

Secure Mobile Sensing Platform - Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)

The integration has been totally done. Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI) data are transmitted to Secure SOXFire through the Secure Mobile Sensing Platform, then can be forwarded to other platforms including Node-RED and Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio).

Ganonymizer – SmileCityReport (App & Server)

The integration is in progress. The images taken by SmileCityReport (App), installed in diverse smartphones running different Operating Systems (Oss), will be anonymized by Ganonymizer. To do that, Ganonymizer has been implemented to export a web API. SmileCityReport (Server) should then be implemented to send the images to the Ganonymizer web API.

Ganonymizer - Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)

The integration is in progress. The images taken by Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI), running at the garbage truck side, will be anonymized by Ganonymizer. To do that, Ganonymizer has been implemented to

export a web API. SmileCityReport (Server) should then be implemented to send the images to the Ganonymizer web API.

IoT crowd-counting and environmental devices - Secure components for devices and gateways

The integration among the IoT devices and the secure components for devices and gateways is currently ongoing. As a starting point, both the crowd counting devices and the environmental ones test their operation sending data to a standard ST-TPM-RASPI. This data is encrypted in the RASPI module and forwarded again to the micro-controller in the IoT device that in turn sends the information encrypted via wireless technology to the other end of the communication link, where it is de-encrypted. Once this process is validated, the interaction with the complete secured component ensues, thus achieving the goal of incorporating extended security for these IoT devices.

IoT crowd-counting and environmental devices - Honeypot (IoTPOt)

The moment the final version of the IoT device incorporating a secure element is up and running, the process continues creating a model of it in order to test it against the Honeypot (IoTPOt) and find out the kind of threats the device will experience when placed in the real world. Given the kind of cross-border interaction required, the employment of Virtual Private Network (VPN) connections is encouraged.

IoT crowd-counting and environmental devices – Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)

A similar approach applies to the interaction with the Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio). In this particular case, the first step consists in having a NDA ready among the involved parties. Afterwards, the data produced by the IoT devices will adjust to the format accepted by Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio).

Park Guide - TST IoT crowd-counting and environmental devices

The Park Guide application developed in the context of Use Case 1 will receive the decrypted information provided by the sensors integrated in the IoT devices and put it into the user interface for end users to better interact with the pilot.

Park Guide – Companion Database and IoT Marketplace

On the other hand, the Park Guide application specifically devised for this Use Case will receive from the Companion Database the information generated by the sensors deployed in the Las Llamas Park and in turn feed the IoT Marketplace with data that will be made available to stakeholders external to the consortium. In addition, the Quorum blockchain framework/Blockchain middleware will interact with the Companion Database to provide additional security and gaming features to foster participation.

SmileCityReport (App & Server) – Secure SOXFire, Companion Database and IoT Marketplace

The main interaction in this case involves the one involving the mobile application SmileCityReport dubbed “SushiRepo”, that will be the one employed by users active in this use case, feeding Secure SOXFire tool and therefore providing data to both the Companion Database and the IoT Marketplace, where stakeholders external to the consortium will have the chance of taking a look into this data and decide whether they find it useful when preparing their very own solutions or prefer to opt out for other alternatives in the marketplace.

Mobile Wallet – Quorum Blockchain framework/Blockchain middleware

The integration of Mobile Wallet with Quorum Blockchain framework/Blockchain middleware was based on Metamask¹(see Figure 2). Using it as a browser extension, the user is able to connect to the Blockchain. We have exploited other features of Metamask and Web3 library in order to authenticate and verify the identity of a user offering more transparency and security. This way, the user can complete a transaction (e.g. transfer of M-Sec tokens) only if he/she has the private/public key of the account and a message/transaction can be signed by a specific user.

Figure 2. Metamask screenshot.

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) - Secure Mobile Sensing Platform

The IDS is developed for Linux operating system (OS) that is the same on which the Secure Mobile Sensing Platform runs. Therefore, the integration is automatic and both runs side-by-side because of being built for the same version of OS.

¹ <https://metamask.io/>

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) - Visualization Tool

Visualization Tool is based on elastic search and its agent are installed in the IDS, where they collect logs from the IDS and uploads them to an elastic server in the cloud.

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) - Honeypot (IoTPOT)

The Honeypot (IoTPOT) is a standalone system that is used as a testbed for analysing attacks on various IoT devices during the designing and testing phase. The integration with IDS is manually conducted by writing the signature patterns observed by the Honeypot (IoTPOT) as signature rules in the IDS.

IoT Marketplace – Mobile Wallet

We have integrated IoT Marketplace with Mobile Wallet which allows the user to have access to the different smart contracts. An important aspect of this integration is the ability of a user to watch the M-Sec Token, which is a Solidity² smart contract running on blockchain. We have explored the use of different Wallets such as the Ethereum Wallet³ (see Figure 3), which allows us to watch, send and transfer Tokens to other users. Using the wallet and logging in using his/her keys, the user can have a visual representation of the information stored in the blockchain (of specific smart contracts) and interact with it in a user friendly manner.

Figure 3. Ethereum Wallet screenshot.

² <https://solidity.readthedocs.io/>

³ <https://ethereum.org/wallets/>

IoT Marketplace – T&R Model engine/tool

We have migrated the Trust and Reputation Model Engine to run on the Blockchain platform. An implementation based on Solidity smart contracts is integrated with the IoT Marketplace running on top of Quorum blockchain platform. This way the user can browse all the registered sensors in the respective smart contract and find information about them such as trust, reputation and feedback from previous purchases. Additional features which ensure that operators of registered sensors will actually provide the data to buyers and data validation have also been considered.

Node-RED – IoT Marketplace

The implementation of M-Sec’s IoT Marketplace has been based on Solidity smart contracts running on top of blockchain. Additionally, the integration with Node-Red and the development of respective Node-Red flows (see Figure 4) allowed the connection with different APIs, web services, IoT devices, sensors and data sources. More than 10 flows have been implemented handling HTTP requests as well (e.g. search of purchases, search registered sensors, buy data, register sensors, transfer tokens etc.).

Figure 4. Node-Red flows.

IoT Marketplace – Quorum Blockchain framework/Blockchain Middleware

An integration process among the IoT Marketplace and the Quorum Blockchain framework/Blockchain Middleware has been conducted. IoT Marketplace communicates with other smart contracts deployed on Quorum blockchain. Additionally, other services, which are part of the Middleware such as Handlers of On-chain/Off-chain data, uploads and accounts are important for the functionality of the Marketplace.

2.4 Components list and their TRL progress

In the Table 3 readers can find a reference table, with value and description, to understand the values on the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale.

Table 3. Technology Readiness Level definitions.

TRL	Definition/Description
9	Actual System Proven Through Successful Mission Operations
8	Actual System Completed and Qualified Through Test and Demonstration
7	System Prototype Demonstration in Relevant Environment
6	System/Subsystem Model or Prototype Demonstration in Relevant Environment
5	Component and/or Breadboard Validation in Relevant Environment
4	Component and/or Breadboard Validation in Laboratory Environment
3	Analytical and Experimental Critical Function and/or Characteristic Proof-of-Concept
2	Technology Concept and/or Application Formulated
1	Basic Principles Observed and Reported

Table 4 recaps the TRL of all the components that are part of the M-Sec prototype. There are three columns in order to appreciate the evolution of them through the years. In year zero the TRL reflects the maturity the asset was brought to M-Sec with. The ones with a value of 1 are assets created specifically for the need of the M-Sec platform.

Table 4. Asset's Technology Readiness Level table.

Asset Name	TRL Year 0	TRL Year 1	TRL Year 2
Ganonymizer	1	3	6
TST IoT environmental devices	3	4	5
TST IoT crowd-counting devices	3	4	5
Park Guide	1	2	5
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	1	4	6
Mobile Wallet	7	7	7
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	3	4	5
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	2	3	6
Visualization Tool	2	3	6
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	2	4	6
Secure SOXFire	2	3	6
SmileCityReport (Server)	2	4	7
YNU Honeypot (IoT POT)	5	6	6
Security Management Tool	1	3	4
Quorum Blockchain framework	4	5	6
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	2	4	7
T&R Model engine/tool	2	3	5
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	2	3	5
Companion Database	1	4	6
Secured components for devices and gateways	3	5	6
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	3	4	5
UC4.1 APP	2	4	6
Caburn Home Monitoring Devices	7	7	7
SmileCityReport - (App)	2	4	7
Node-RED	9	9	9

2.5 SRL table

In the Table 5 readers might check a reference table, with value and description, to understand all values on System Readiness Level (SRL) as employed in this document.

Table 5. System Readiness Level descriptions.

SRL	Definition/Description
5	Operations & Support
4	Production & Development
3	System Development & Demonstration
2	Technology Development
1	Concept Refinement

Table 7 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Components SRL array for the overall M-Sec platform. The calculations have been made by the methodology written in deliverable D2.5 “Integration Plan” in section “2.2 Calculation”. As mentioned in that section, a Component SRL gives a picture of how well a specific component is integrated in the whole system (or subsystem, in the case of Use Cases), while the Composite SRL is the average of the Component SRLs and provides a metric for identifying the overall progress of the integration of all the components of the system (or subsystem). Composite SRLs are calculated on a scale from 0 to 1 (normalized value) and are then matched to a 5-levels scale (similar to the case of the TRL and IRL scales, which have 9 levels though). To translate the 0 to 1 scale to a 1 to 5 scale (the one presented in Table 5), an SRL Matching Model (Table 6) is used to map the decimal values to whole number values.

Table 6. SRL Matching Table.

SRL	Definition/Description	Composite SRL
5	Operations & Support	0,9 to 1,00
4	Production & Development	0,8 to 0,89
3	System Development & Demonstration	0,6 to 0,79
2	Technology Development	0,4 to 0,59
1	Concept Refinement	0,1 to 0,39

Table 7. M-Sec’s platform System Readiness Level.

Asset Name	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Caburn Home Monitoring Devices	7	2	88	1,09	0,54
Companion Database	6	7	135	1,67	0,24
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	6	3	96	1,19	0,40
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	5	7	157	1,94	0,28
Ganonymizer	6	3	93	1,15	0,38
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	6	4	162	2,00	0,50
IoT Marketplace	7	9	238	2,94	0,33
Mobile Wallet	7	3	134	1,65	0,55
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	5	3	75	0,93	0,31
Node-RED	9	5	169	2,09	0,42
Park Guide	5	5	88	1,09	0,22
Quorum Blockchain/Blockchain middleware	6	10	239	2,95	0,30
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	6	6	154	1,90	0,32
Secure SOXFire	6	11	240	2,96	0,27
Secured components for devices and gateways	6	5	88	1,09	0,22
Security Management Tool	4	6	68	0,84	0,14
SmileCityReport (App)	7	2	84	1,04	0,52
SmileCityReport (Server)	7	5	142	1,75	0,35
T&R Model engine/tool	5	2	59	0,73	0,36
Visualization Tool	6	2	90	1,11	0,56
TST IoT crowd-counting devices	5	5	77	0,95	0,19
TST IoT environmental devices	5	5	77	0,95	0,19
UC4.1 APP	6	3	96	1,19	0,40
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	5	5	147	1,81	0,36
Honeypot (IoTPOt)	6	3	114	1,41	0,47

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for the overall M-Sec platform is 0,35, which is mapped to an SRL of level 1 – Concept Refinement. However, this value is pretty close to 0,40, which is mapped to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development.

3. Integration readiness level analysis

3.1 Use Case 1

Short description for Use Case 1 and summary of requirements

The use case will deploy a series of novel IoT devices in selected locations in the city of Santander both to retrieve interesting environmental data along with a measurement of noise levels, and to be capable of sketching crowd heat maps, using as a source of information the number of mobile phones in the area.

- Users will check measurements through a dedicated webpage / app.
- Possibility to rate the information received.
- Introduce gaming features and rewards.

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- Deployed devices should not impact the scenario negatively nor affect the daily operations as they are before their deployment.
- The service should facilitate the visualisation of real-time information in a map or in a list (physical sensing information).
- The service should facilitate the visualisation of historical information in a map or in a list (physical sensing information).
- The application should provide a tool to analyse data and extract statistics in a simple and easily understandable way for the city economic development division and event organisers.
- The local architecture should be scalable and integrated with others.

The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The mobile phone IDs of end-users interacting with the city spots where the pilot is carried out should be anonymized.
- The associated web application should protect the privacy of the end-user, propose several levels of management of personal data, and give the option of modifying the privacy parameters any time.

Interaction diagram

The expected interactions in this use case will focus on the ones happening among the IoT devices designed by TST to keep track of environmental measurements and provide a figure related to the number of people gathering in selected spots. The analysis of potential attacks to these devices will be carried out through the Honeypot (IoT POT), as depicted in Figure 5 below:

Figure 5. Interaction diagram of Use Case 1.

Use Case IRL matrix

All interactions points that are expected to take place between all the assets of the Use Case 1 can be seen in the Table 8 interaction matrix. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in previous deliverable D2.5), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 8. Interactions matrix of Use Case 1.

Use Case 1

	Park guide	TST IoT crowd-counting devices	TST IoT environmental devices	Companion Database	Node-RED	Secure SOXFire	Quorum Blockchain framework	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	T&R Model engine/tool	Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	Secured components for devices and gateways	Honeypot (IoT POT)	Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	Security Management Tool
Park Guide		3	3	1			1							
TST IoT crowd-counting devices						1				1		1		
TST IoT environmental devices						1				1		1		
Companion Database					1	5							1	
Node-RED						1	1	2						
Secure SOXFire														
Quorum Blockchain framework							6					1		
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware								2						
T&R Model engine/tool														
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)														
Secured components for devices and gateways											3			
Honeypot (IoT POT)														
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)														
Security Management Tool														

Use Case SRL table

Table 9 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 1.

Table 9. System Readiness Level of Use Case 1.

Asset Name	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Park Guide	5	5	88	1,09	0,22
TST IoT crowd-counting devices	5	5	77	0,95	0,19
TST IoT environmental devices	5	5	77	0,95	0,19
Companion Database	6	5	99	1,22	0,24
Node-RED	9	4	104	1,28	0,32
Secure SOXFire	6	3	69	0,85	0,28
Quorum Blockchain/Blockchain middleware	6	6	141	1,74	0,29
IoT Marketplace	7	5	123	1,52	0,30
T&R Model engine/tool	5	2	59	0,73	0,36
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	5	2	63	0,78	0,39
Secured components for devices and gateways	6	4	82	1,01	0,25
HoneyPot (IoTPOt)	6	2	72	0,89	0,44
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	5	4	61	0,75	0,19
Security Management Tool	4	2	42	0,52	0,26

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 1 is 0,28, which is translated to an SRL of level 1 – Concept Refinement.

3.2 Use Case 2

Short description for Use Case 2 and summary of requirements

Use Case 2, “Home monitoring & Wellbeing Tele-assistance for active and independent aging people”, is based in the Worldline’s asset dubbed Connected Care, a solution designed to improve quality of life of elderly people by offering services based on monitoring their home activity and helping them to live independently at home while offering security and peace of mind to their families.

With Connected Care, users are monitored and looked after using home sensor devices such as a smart plug, bed occupancy sensor, window/door open sensor, and motion sensor. All data generated by these sensors are collected and analysed on an ongoing basis by tele-operators of the tele-assistance company in charge of taking immediate action if necessary.

The main value added and the objective of the use case and its associated pilot is to ensure through the M-Sec platform a trusted environment concerning all the sensitive data collected by these devices and privacy protection.

Therefore, the two main goals of the use case that will be probed during the execution of the pilot will be:

- Improvement of quality of life of elderly people who live alone and are not familiar with the use of new technologies.
- Improvement of data security and integrity through the use of M-Sec assets in the different elements that compound the service. For example, components (sensors, cloud systems) involved in the data stream dissemination need to be tamper-proof to prevent malicious attacks on devices.

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should let users collect information about their home activity (e.g. windows open sensor).
- The system should store massive information (such as temperature per second) in an efficient way, taking into account that not all data are expected to be recorded/stored forever.
- The system should store information (such as access to data) in a way that ensures this information will not be forgotten, and with mechanisms that allow third parties to verify that this information is correct and true.

The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should have an access control policy, binding the users with different profiles, each with different access privileges to data (the owner of the data, a person assigned by them to consult their data –family member or professional-, software administrator, technical support, security officer, etc.)
- The system should have several policies of access to the data, depending on the role of the user and the data the user is trying to access to. Anonymous users should be given no access to any data related to users.
- The system should have a dashboard for matching roles to policies and privileges of access.
- The system should support an easy-to-use mechanism that enables the owner of the data to grant privileges of access to other users in an understandable way.
- The system should support mechanisms for authentication and authorisation of the users, including updates of the users' proofs of access privileges.
- The system should include security measures that protect data transmitted over the network at the application level against eavesdropping (encryption and peer authentication).

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram in Figure 6 shows how each asset interacts with the others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 6. Interaction diagram of Use Case 2

Use Case IRL matrix

In Table 10 interaction matrix, can be seen all the interaction points between all the assets that the use case have. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described deliverable D2.5), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 10: Interactions matrix of Use Case 2

Use Case 2	Worldline Connected Care Assistance	Companion Database	Caburn Home Monitoring Devices	Secure SOXFire	Node-RED	Quorum Blockchain framework	Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	T&R Model engine/tool	Security Management Tool
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	6				1	5	5				
Companion Database				5							1
Caburn Home Monitoring Devices							5				
Secure SOXFire							6				1
Node-RED					5	2		6			
Quorum Blockchain framework											
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)											
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)											1
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware									2		
T&R Model engine/tool											
Security Management Tool											

Use Case SRL table

Table 11 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 2.

Table 11. System Readiness Level of Use Case 2.

Asset Name	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	7	5	119	1,47	0,29
Companion Database	6	4	94	1,16	0,29
Caburn Home Monitoring Devices	6	4	162	2,00	0,50
Secure SOXFire	6	4	126	1,56	0,39
Node-RED	6	5	109	1,35	0,27
Quorum Blockchain/ Blockchain middleware	6	2	90	1,11	0,56
Modal Transition System Analyser (MTSA)	6	4	132	1,63	0,41
Eclipse sensiNact platform (and Studio)	6	2	60	0,74	0,37
IoT Marketplace	4	3	49	0,60	0,20
T&R Model engine/tool	5	2	59	0,73	0,36
Security Management Tool	6	2	96	1,19	0,59

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 2 is 0,38, which is mapped to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development.

3.3 Use Case 3

Short description for Use Case 3 and summary of requirements

This use case provides a client application that allows urban environment monitoring entities (for example, local governments) to visualise spatially and temporarily dense environmental data. Using the application, the entities are enabled to serve their citizens with sophisticated environment monitoring better. In this scenario, an automotive sensing platform is used to generate real-time environmental sensor data streams from all over the city of Fujisawa, leveraging hundred mobile sensing trucks.

This use case illustrates how the M-Sec platform secures such a mobile sensing platform.

The Scenario specific objectives/requirements are as follows:

- The system should collect environment sensor data.
- The system should be able to handle a large number of data streams concurrently.
- The system should be able to transfer the data streams in real-time.
- The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:
- The system needs to secure the heterogeneous components involved in the data stream dissemination, so that they are not hacked by malicious attackers.
- The system needs to secure the data streams so that the data is not tampered in the network between their source and destination.
- The system should protect the data streams from malicious attackers at the edge and distributed cloud platform.
- The system should disseminate the environment data stream to citizens securely.

- The system should not harm citizens' privacy; thus, an automated privacy protection mechanism should be provided.
- The system should grant access only to those with valid access rights.

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram in Figure 7 shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 7: Interaction diagram of Use Case 3

Use Case IRL matrix

In Table 12 interaction matrix, can be seen all the interaction points between the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 3. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in deliverable D2.5), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 12: Interactions matrix of Use Case 3

Use Case 3	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	Companion Database	Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	Secure SOXFire	Visualization Tool	Quorum Blockchain framework	Secured components for devices and gateways	Security Management Tool	T&R Model engine/tool	Honeypot (IoT POT)
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware				1		6		1	2		
Companion Database				1		5		1			
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)			5		6						7
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform				6			1				
Secure SOXFire						1					
Visualization Tool											
Quorum Blockchain framework											
Secured components for devices and gateways											
Security Management Tool											
T&R Model engine/tool											
Honeypot (IoT POT)											

Use Case SRL table

Table 13 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 3.

Table 13. System Readiness Level of Use Case 3.

Companion Database	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
IoT Marketplace	7	5	119	1,47	0,29
Companion Database	6	4	94	1,16	0,29
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	6	4	162	2,00	0,50
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	6	4	126	1,56	0,39
Secure SOXFire	6	5	109	1,35	0,27
Visualization Tool	6	2	90	1,11	0,56
Quorum Blockchain/ Blockchain middleware	6	4	132	1,63	0,41
Secured components for devices and gateways	6	2	60	0,74	0,37
Security Management Tool	4	3	49	0,60	0,20
T&R Model engine/tool	5	2	59	0,73	0,36
Honeypot (IoT POT)	6	2	96	1,19	0,59

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 3 is 0,38, which is translated to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development.

3.4 Use Case 4

Short description for Use Case 4 and summary of requirements

In this use case, “Hyper-connected citizen care applications” will be created for a range of different purposes and for different stakeholders. On the one hand, a government officers’ application will collect city-related data (such as urban waste generation per household, pedestrian flow or traffic flow data, etc.) through the M-Sec architecture and analyse the data to produce value-added data that affect citizens efficiently. Citizens’ applications, on the other hand, will consume that value-added data to empower their decision on related topics towards better (physical, mental or social) wellbeing or Quality of Life (QoL).

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should collect heterogeneous data on citizens’ life in real time.
- The system should be able to handle a large number of data streams concurrently.
- The system should be able to transfer the data stream in real time.
- The local architecture should be scalable and can be integrated with others.
- Deployed devices will not impact negatively in the scenario nor affect the daily operations as they are before their deployment.
- The associated web application should provide and visualise environment information collected over the city.
- The application should provide a tool to analyse data and extract statistics in a simple and easily understandable way for the city environment division and citizens.
- The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:
- The system needs to secure the heterogeneous components involved in the data stream dissemination so that they are not hacked by malicious attackers.
- The system needs to secure the data streams, so that the data is not tempered in the network between their source and destination.
- The system should not harm citizens’ privacy; thus, an automated privacy protection mechanism should be provided.
- The system should disseminate the data stream to municipalities and citizens securely
- The system should protect the data streams from malicious attackers at the edge and distributed cloud platform
- The system should grant accesses from whom own a valid access right
- The cloud system should store the data securely so that they are not disclosed to any party without permission

Pilot 4.1- Interaction diagram

The integration diagram in Figure 8 shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 8: Interaction diagram of Use Case 4.1

Pilot 4.1 - Use Case IRL matrix

In Table 14 interaction matrix, can be seen all the interaction points between the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 4.1.

Table 14: Interactions matrix of Use Case 4.1

Use Case 4.1	Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	Ganonymizer	Companion Database	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	Secure SOXFire	Quorum Blockchain framework	Secured components for devices and gateways	Security Management Tool	T&R Model engine/tool	UC4.1 APP	Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	Honeypot (IoTPOt)	Visualization Tool
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	3			4										
Ganonymizer														
Companion Database					1	5	1	1						
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware					1	6	1	2						
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform					6	1					5			
Secure SOXFire						1				6				
Quorum Blockchain framework														
Secured components for devices and gateways														
Security Management Tool														
T&R Model engine/tool														
UC4.1 APP														
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)												7	6	
Honeypot (IoTPOt)														
Visualization Tool														

Pilot 4.1 – Use Case SRL table

Table 15 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 4.1.

Table 15. System Readiness Level of Use Case 4.1.

Asset Name	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	6	3	96	1,19	0,40
Ganonymizer	6	2	72	0,89	0,44
Companion Database	6	5	100	1,23	0,25
IoT Marketplace	7	5	119	1,47	0,29
Secure Mobile Sensing Platform	6	5	150	1,85	0,37
Secure SOXFire	6	6	145	1,79	0,30
Quorum Blockchain/ Blockchain middleware	6	4	132	1,63	0,41
Secured components for devices and gateways	6	2	60	0,74	0,37
Security Management Tool	4	3	49	0,60	0,20
T&R Model engine/tool	5	2	59	0,73	0,36
UC4.1 APP	6	3	96	1,19	0,40
Intrusion Detection System (IDS)	6	4	162	2,00	0,50
Honeypot (IoTPOt)	6	2	96	1,19	0,59
Visualization Tool	6	2	90	1,11	0,56

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 4.1 is 0,39, which is translated to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development.

Pilot 4.2 - Interaction diagram

The integration diagram in Figure 9 shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 9: Interaction diagram of Use Case 4.2

Pilot 4.2 - Use Case IRL matrix

In Table 16 interaction matrix, can be seen all the interaction points between the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 4.2.

Table 16: Interactions matrix of Use Case 4.2

Use Case 4.2	Ganonymizer	Companion Database	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	Secure SOXFire	Quorum Blockchain framework	Security Management Tool	T&R Model engine/tool	SmileCityReport (App)	SmileCityReport (Server)
Ganonymizer									3
Companion Database			1	5	1				
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware			1	6	1	2			
Secure SOXFire				1					6
Quorum Blockchain framework									
Security Management Tool									
T&R Model engine/tool									
SmileCityReport (App)									3
SmileCityReport (Server)									

Pilot 4.2 - Use Case SRL table

Table 17 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 4.2.

Table 17. System Readiness Level of Use Case 4.2.

companion Database	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Ganonymizer	6	2	75	0,93	0,46
Companion Database	6	4	94	1,16	0,29
IoT Marketplace	7	5	119	1,47	0,29
Secure SOXFire	6	5	115	1,42	0,28
Quorum Blockchain/ Blockchain middleware	6	4	132	1,63	0,41
Security Management Tool	4	3	49	0,60	0,20
T&R Model engine/tool	5	2	59	0,73	0,36
SmileCityReport (App)	7	2	84	1,04	0,52
SmileCityReport (Server)	7	4	138	1,70	0,43

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 4.2 is 0,36, which is translated to an SRL of level 1 – Concept Refinement.

3.5 Use Case 5

Short description for Use Case 5 and summary of requirements

This use case focuses on creating a marketplace to distribute data while ensuring confidentiality, integrity, availability, and privacy of data following GDPR/PIPA regulations so that people or organizations in EU and Japan can utilize the data more securely and effectively. Data to be exchanged in the marketplace are:

- Data from citizens and visitors: Purchase data, health data collected by pedometers, personal data collected by smartphones, data collected by questionnaires.
- Local government data: Statistic data, local information such as photos or reports collected by city staff
- Web data: Any data automatically collected from the internet (environmental data, etc.)
- IoT data: Data collected from IoT devices (cameras, etc.) owned by companies or local governments.

Requirements:

- The local architecture should be processed securely.
- The cloud system should store the data securely and could be accessed from EU and Japan.
- The devices should be used to collect user's data, such as behaviour characteristic data.

The marketplace will be secured by using Blockchain technology.

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram in Figure 10 shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 10: Interaction diagram of Use Case 5

Use Case IRL matrix

In Table 18 interaction matrix, can be seen all the interaction points between the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 3. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in deliverable D2.5), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 18: Interactions matrix of Use Case 5

Use Case 5

	Companion Database	SmileCityReport (App)	SmileCityReport (Server)	Ganonymizer	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	Secure SOXFire	Mobile Wallet	Quorum Blockchain framework	Security Management Tool
Companion Database						1	5	1	
SmileCityReport (App)		3							
SmileCityReport (Server)			3			6			1
Ganonymizer									
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware						5	6		
Secure SOXFire									1
Mobile Wallet							6		
Quorum Blockchain framework									
Security Management Tool									

Use Case SRL table

Table 19 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 5.

Table 19. System Readiness Level of Use Case 5.

Asset Name	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Companion Database	6	4	94	1,16	0,29
SmileCityReport (App)	7	2	84	1,04	0,52
SmileCityReport (Server)	7	5	142	1,75	0,35
Ganonymizer	6	2	75	0,93	0,46
IoT Marketplace	7	3	134	1,65	0,55
Secure SOXFire	6	4	106	1,31	0,33
Mobile Wallet	7	3	134	1,65	0,55
Quorum Blockchain/ Blockchain middleware	6	4	168	2,07	0,52
Security Management Tool	4	4	55	0,68	0,17

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 5 is 0,42, which is translated to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development.

3.6 Use Case 6

Short description for Use Case 6 and summary of requirements

This use case takes into account the current knowledge and habits of citizens in both Santander and Fujisawa in order to promote a participatory environment in which they contribute to reflect the pulse of every city

- Personally reporting on various events
 - Promoting preferred spots
 - Announcing their activity in selected events

Therefore, Use Case 6 will create and implement the participatory environment in which citizens of Santander and Fujisawa provide their reports on various events.

- Citizens will feel more involved in the daily operations of their corresponding cities.
- Municipal officers will get an additional information resource to help them carry out their jobs. Municipalities will enjoy of a different channel to promote themselves.

Interaction diagram

The expected interaction in this use case, depicted in Figure 11, will focus on the one happening among the applications which were originally deployed in each one of the cities involved in M-Sec, and that will act as the foundation of the application, which will be developed in Use Case 6.

Figure 11: Interaction diagram of Use Case 6

The main interaction in this case involves the one involving the mobile application dubbed “SmileCityReport (SushiRepo)”, that will be the one employed by users active in this use case, feeding Secure SOXFire tool and therefore providing data to both the Companion Database and the IoT Marketplace, where stakeholders external to the consortium will have the chance of taking a look into this data and decide whether they find it useful when preparing their very own solutions or prefer to opt out for other alternatives in the marketplace.

In parallel, the Mobile Wallet application will use blockchain framework and middleware to feed the Companion Database and in turn forward additional data to the IoT Marketplace.

Use Case IRL matrix

In the Table 20 interaction matrix we can see the interaction points between all the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 6. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in previous deliverable D2.5), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 20: Interactions matrix of Use Case 6

Use Case 6

	Companion Database	SmileCityReport (App)	SmileCityReport (Server)	Ganonymizer	IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware	Secure SOXFire	Mobile Wallet	Quorum Blockchain framework	Security Management Tool
Companion Database						1	5	1	
SmileCityReport (App)			3						
SmileCityReport (Server)				3		6			1
Ganonymizer									
IoT Marketplace/Blockchain middleware							5	6	
Secure SOXFire									1
Mobile Wallet								6	
Quorum Blockchain framework									
Security Management Tool									

Use Case SRL table

Table 21 recaps the calculations performed to extract the Component SRL array for Use Case 6.

Table 21. System Readiness Level of Use Case 6.

Asset Name	TRL	Links	Non-normalized SRLi	Normalized SRLi	Component SRL
Companion Database	6	4	94	1,16	0,29
SmileCityReport (App)	7	2	84	1,04	0,52
SmileCityReport (Server)	7	5	142	1,75	0,35
Ganonymizer	6	2	75	0,93	0,46
IoT Marketplace	7	3	134	1,65	0,55
Secure SOXFire	6	4	106	1,31	0,33
Mobile Wallet	7	3	134	1,65	0,55
Quorum Blockchain/ Blockchain middleware	6	4	168	2,07	0,52
Security Management Tool	4	4	55	0,68	0,17

After doing the calculations, the Composite SRL for Use Case 6 is 0,42, which is translated to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development.

4. Conclusions

At this stage and following the plan from the deliverable D2.5, the first version of M-Sec has been accomplished. The development in the integration points have been initiated, and by now, some of them are already at a good level of progress.

Some core modules/components/assets are interacting successfully with each other, and more are expected in the following months. In the next period (April-October, 2020), focus will be given on fully integrating all other assets and cover all business requirements of the project.

Moreover, focus on testing and ensuring a stable and efficient system to be offered to end-users will be one of the main priorities.

It should be noted that all of the subsystems (Use Case ones) and the whole M-Sec system already present a Composite SRL close to 40% which corresponds to an SRL of level 2 – Technology Development. For the project to be successful, it is planned for all subsystems and the whole system to reach a Composite SRL close to 70%, which corresponds to an SRL of level 3 –System Development and Demonstration, which is a typical level for successful Horizon 2020 projects.